

HARVEST AND QUALITY OF CORN FOR GRAIN AT VARIOUS NORMS OF MINERAL FERTILIZERS

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ABSTRACT

By results of researches in the conditions of the Central Polissia on soddy podzolic soils mineral fertilization positively affected productivity of corn for grain, fertilization of optimum norm of N₁₂₀ P₆₀ K₈₀ made 7.56 t/hectare that is 73.4% higher concerning control variant, and the highest productivity was received on option N₁₅₀, which made 7.59 t/hectare that is 74% higher than control option.

The analysis of quality indicators showed that also the mineral system of fertilizer with optimum norm was the best N₁₂₀ P₆₀ K₈₀, especially the content of conditional collecting protein – 9.09 c/hectare, the protein made 12.1%, 48.4 c/hectare collecting protein feed units per one hectare of crops.

Keywords: corn, crude protein, mineral fertilizers, fertilizer options, quality of products.

Relevance of subject. In Ukraine there are favorable soil and climatic conditions for cultivation of extremely great opportunities and wide use of grain culture as corn.

On condition of high culture of agrotechnology, nutrition, the optimum modes of irrigation it is capable to give more 100-120 c/hectare of grain. And at the correct cultivation as raw culture, promotes clarification of crops from weeds.

Introducing intensive technologies, energy saving, ecologically safe, using high-yielding grades and hybrids in short terms and at the high agrotechnical level, increase in gross collecting grain of corn is possible.

One of ultrafast environmental factors which affect not only productivity, but also quality of products keeping, raising at the same time indicators of fertility of soils rationally, scientifically reasonably to use the

greatest richness of Ukraine, fertile soils, highly productive hybrids which are adapted to agroecological conditions and especially fertilizers.

Purpose of researches consists in need to establish optimum doses of mineral fertilizers which improve growth development, efficiency of plants of corn and increase quality of the received products.

Research was done on conditions of Ltd company "Velykofosnianske" village Velyka Fosnia Korostenyky district of the Zhytomyr region. This region of the Central Polissia in the climatic relation is moderately continental, soft, damp. It is promoted by significant amount of the rivers and to decrease in continentality of climate. Placement of fields of farm is satisfactory for cultivation of crops of the Polissia area.

The researched soil: sod-podzolic sandy with contents: N – 110 mg/kg, P₂O₅ – 124 mg/kg, K₂O – 89 mg/kg, reaction of soil solution – 5.6.

Research scheme

option No.	Fertilizer options in crop rotation
1.	Without fertilizers (control option)
2.	N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ ;
3.	N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ ;
4.	N ₁₅₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ .

Results of researches. Plants use available nutrients for nutrition from the soil. Depending on structure and properties of the soil the general reserve and amount of available nutrients in different soils are not identical therefore for increase in amount of available nutrients in the soil it is necessary to use fertilizers. In the course of nutrition, the close interrelation and interaction between plants, the soil and fertilizers is observed [1, 3].

Important issue concerning nutrition habits of plants which need to be considered for correct to establish ways and terms of application of fertilizers and their norm. Considering importance of this question, it

was decided that for cultivation of corn it is necessary to investigate the nutritious mode of the soil.

Corn is one of cultures needing the increased quantity of elements of substances. Corn to the nitrogen which is part of protein is especially exacting. Acquires nitrogen corn during all growing season, and the greatest number from phase of 7-8 leaves. At lack of soils of readily available compounds of nitrogen, we can observe that growth of corn slows down, and its leaves turn yellow therefore the harvest, both grain, and green material can sharply decrease [7].

Negatively unilateral nitric food affects efficiency of crops, namely then the discrepancy between rapid growth and the slowed-down development of plants is

observed. Such crops often fall, the specific weight of heads of cabbage in productivity of elevated weight considerably is lost, late maturing of plants, and the productivity of grain as a rule is low [5].

Fertilizers which get to the soil are exposed to different biological, physical and chemical transformations. In the soil the nutritious elements which are got from fertilizers are exposed to solubility, then their ability to movement in the soil, as a result availability to plants increases. Differently these processes take place in different soils. At the same time fertilizers influence the soil very strongly, namely: change reaction of soil solution, enrich with nutrients, intensity and the nature of microbiological processes and other properties of the soil that defines its fertility. Therefore, knowledge of structure of the soil and its properties, chemical and biological, physical and chemical processes which happen in it is important for determination of nature of transformation in the soil of fertilizers, features on various soils of their action and consequently,

for the most effective and correct use of mineral fertilizers according to requirements of soil conditions and plants [4].

For forming of big crop of grain of modern sorts and hybrids of corn it is necessary to provide optimum quantity of plants and productive stems per one area, reached by the corresponding norm of seeding. Both at liquefied, and at extremely dense crops, the harvest of corn decreases [4]. Norms of corn seeding depend on soil-climatic conditions, predecessors, fertilizers, biology of grade or hybrid. It is known that optimum density of plants and enough nutrients in the soil – the major conditions on which the harvest of crops depends [3]. Therefore, studying of reaction of modern sorts and hybrids of corn to various backgrounds of mineral food on the level of productivity is very important.

By results of researches we observe that fertilizers have positive impact on productivity of corn (tab. 1).

Tab. 1

Impact of systems of fertilizer on corn grain yield

Research options	Scheme of research	Productivity, t/hectare			
		Years of research		average	± to control option
		2020	2021		
1	Without fertilizers	4.15	4.57	4.36	100
2	N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ ;	5.83	6.49	6.16	141.3
3	N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ ;	7, 2 8	7.84	7.56	173.4
4	N ₁₅₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ .	7.26	7.92	7.59	174.0
HOLES 0,5 0.33 0.28					

Using of different norms of mineral fertilizers, apparently from tab. 1, positively affecting productivity of grain of corn. The smallest productivity was observed on control and averaged 4.36 t/hectare.

Using of mineral fertilizers with the smallest standard of productivity of grain of corn in two years averaged 6.16 t/hectare that is 41.3% higher than control. Application of fertilizers with optimum norm made 7.56 t/hectare that is 73.4% higher concerning control, and the highest productivity was noted on option with high norm of nitrogen and was 7.59 t/hectare that is 74% higher than control option.

In the last option of research, the productivity changed slightly and was in error limits. The difference in two last years averaged 0.3 t/hectare or 0.6% that allowed to consider the received results of productivity are almost identical.

The quality of commodity grain of corn also in

many respects depends on harvesting time. From milk wax till maturity protein content and irreplaceable amino acids in grain decreases, and the content of fat and starch grows and reaches maximum at stage of full maturing [39].

The maintenance of crude protein is one of the most important indicators of quality of grain of corn. Use of small doses of nitrogen before crops can increase corn grains protein content. By results of research showed that the maintenance of crude protein in grains of corn increases at grades with mineral fertilizers. The smallest maintenance of crude protein was on control option and made 9.2%. Two options of fertilizer with N were the best $_{120}P_{45}K_{30}$, which made 12.1, and $N_{150}P_{45}K_{30}$ – 12.3 that for 131.5 and is 133.7% higher concerning control. (tab. 2). At introduction of the highest doses of nitrogen we noticed the maximum maintenance of crude protein.

Tab. 2

Impact of mineral fertilizer on quality indicators (2020-2021)

Research options	Content in grain, %				
	crude fat	dry matter	crude protein	crude cellulose	crude ashes
Without fertilizers	6.13	23.6	9.2	4.18	1.6
N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ ;	6.70	25.0	10.4	4.84	1.7
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ ;	6.74	26.7	12.1	5.07	1.8
N ₁₅₀ P ₆₀ K ₈₀ .	6.74	27.1	12.3	5.37	1.8

The similar trend appeared on all other indicators of quality, namely: dry matter, crude ashes, cellulose and fat, and again the best found two options of fertilizer normal of nitrogen N₁₂₀ and N₁₅₀.

On the basis of the above it is possible to draw the following conclusion, namely introduction of N₁₂₀ P₄₅ K₃₀ and N₁₅₀ P₄₅ K₃₀ increased the maintenance of protein, dry matter of grain of corn and conditional collecting from crops hectare.

Conclusion. Mineral fertilization positively affected productivity, use of optimum norm made 7.56 t/hectare that is 73.4% higher concerning control, and the highest productivity was received on option N₁₅₀, which made 7.59 t/hectare that is 74% higher than control option.

The analysis of quality indicators showed that the mineral system of fertilizer with optimum norm was the best also N₁₂₀ P₆₀ K₈₀, namely content of conditional collecting protein – 9.09 c/hectare, the protein made 12.1%, 48.4 c/hectare collecting protein feed units per one hectare of crops.

References

1. And gafon E. The system of fertilizer of hybrids of corn at cultivation on grain / E.V. Agafonov, A.A. Batakov//Forage production. – 2002. No. 5. page 18-20.
2. Getmanets A. Ya. Influence of fertilizers on efficiency and quality of various hybrids of corn / A.Ya. Getmanets, V.I. Zolotov, N.A. Chernyavskaya, A.K. Ponomarenko//Agrochemistry. 2005. No. 6. Page 63-69.
3. Goncharenko D. F. The composition of seed fertilizer for corn in the zone of insufficient moisture / F. Goncharenko//Agronomics. 2006. No. 5. page 84-87.
4. Garden M. M. Scientific and methodical recommendations about optimization mineral food of crops and strategy of fertilizer / M.M. Ogorodny, O.I. Bondar, A.V. Bykin [etc.]; - M.: LLC Alefa, 2004. – 140 c.
5. Gospodarenko G.M. Bases integrated use of fertilizers / G.M. Hozyaychenko. – To.: CJSC Nichlava, 2002. – 344 pages.
6. Gospodarenko G. Corn fertilizer / G. Gospodarenko//Agrobusiness today. – 2010. No. 10. page 18-19.
7. Swarty O.F. Technologies and technology projects cultivation of the main crops: studies. grant / O.F. Smogly, O.A. Derecha, P.A. Ryabchuk [etc.] – Zhytomyr: Publishing house "DVUZ "State Agroecological University", 2007. – Page 22-27.